

Extraction-spectrophotometric Determination of Manganese(II) with *N*-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol

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Many spectrophotometric methods of determination of manganese based on the formation of complexes with organic reagents have been reported¹, which are neither sensitive nor selective as a large number of metals interfere. The interference due to these metals have been overcome using *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPBA) as a selective extracting reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of manganese(II). The sensitivity of the present method is increased remarkably by the addition of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN).

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of Mn^{II}-HDPBA and Mn^{II}-PAN complexes show λ_{max} at 400 and 555 nm. Among various polar and non-polar organic solvents tried for the extraction of the complex, chloroform was chosen as solvent because of selective extraction and greater colour intensity of the complex. The optimum pH range for the quantitative extraction of Mn^{II}-HDPBA complex and full colour development of Mn^{II}-PAN complex in chloroform and aqueous solution were found to be 8.0–9.5 and 9.0–11.2 respectively. Therefore, experiments were carried out at pH 9.0 ± 0.2 and 10.0 ± 0.2 respectively.

Mn^{II} was found to be stripped back into aqueous medium from Mn^{II}-HDPBA complex when chloroform extract of the complex was shaken with 2 ml of 1–3 *M* HCl. In practice, 2 ml of 2 *M* HCl was used for all stripping work. This aqueous solution after adjusting the pH to 10.0 ± 0.2 with borate buffer (5–8 ml) was reacted with PAN solution and the appearance of haziness was cleared off upon dilution with distilled water.

It was found that $(0.69\text{--}1.73) \times 10^{-2}$ *M* HDPBA and $(0.53\text{--}1.06) \times 10^{-4}$ *M* PAN solutions could be used without any adverse effect on the absorbance of the complex. A 1.0×10^{-2} *M* HDPBA solution in chloroform and 0.8×10^{-4} *M* PAN solution in methanol were used for extraction and colour development of the complexes.

A minimum shaking time of 1 min was needed for maximum extraction of the Mn^{II}-HDPBA complex at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ$). The Mn^{II}-PAN complex was stable upto 6 h. The absorbance of Mn^{II}-HDPBA complex was unaffected when the volume ratio of organic to aqueous phase was varied between 2 : 1 to 1 : 5.

The Mn^{II}-HDPBA and Mn^{II}-PAN complexes obeyed Beer's law upto 2.4 ppm in chloroform and 0.7 ppm in

aqueous methanol solution respectively. The molar absorptivity values of these complexes were found to be $1.51 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 400 nm in chloroform and $4.94 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 555 nm in aqueous methanol solution respectively. The precision of the method was checked by taking 10 replicate measurements, each containing $0.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ Mn}^{\text{II}}$. The Sandell's sensitivity of the method is $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The limit for the detection of Mn^{II} is $0.02 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in aqueous solution. The relative standard deviation of the method is $\pm 1.4\%$.

The stoichiometry of the Mn^{II}-HDPBA and Mn^{II}-PAN complexes were determined by curve-fitting method. The data show that the two molecules of HDPBA and PAN were required to the each Mn^{II} ion for the formation of Mn^{II}-HDPBA and Mn^{II}-PAN complexes, thus the ratio of metal to reagent was 1 : 2 in both the cases. The 1 : 2 ratio of Mn^{II} to PAN in aqueous medium and organic solution was reported earlier².

The overall reaction mechanism can be written as

where subscripts o, o' and o'' denote chloroform, methanol and water + methanol mixture respectively.

The effect of diverse ions on the determination of $0.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1} \text{ Mn}^{\text{II}}$ was examined and the tolerance limit (ppm) of various ions (shown in parenthesis) are as follows: Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} (1); Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} (5); Fe^{III} (8); As^V and V^V (50); Bi^{III} (80); Sb^{III} and Cr^{III} (100); Ba^{II} and Al^{III} (150); Co^{II}, Ca^{II} and iodide (200); Mo^{VI} (250); Mg^{II}, Se^{IV} and phosphate (300); bicarbonate and carbonate (400); persulphate, sulphate and nitrate (500); thiourea and oxalate (700); citrate (1000); EDTA and tartrate (1200). The serious interference due to Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} could be masked by adding 1 ml of 1% (w/v) EDTA solution prior to the extraction.

The method was applied for the determination of manganese(II) in industrial waste water, coal ash and cement dust. The coal ash sample was treated with H₂SO₄, HNO₃, HClO₄ and HF³ and the residue dissolved in HCl. Whereas the cement dust sample was digested with aqua regia⁴, the excess HNO₃ removed by heating with concentrated HCl and the dried mass was dissolved in de-ionised water. 100-ml in a volumetric flask. The metal content determined as

in the above described procedure. The results (Table 1) were in good agreement with that of the AAS method.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF Mn^{II} IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES

Sample	Mn^{II} found (ppm)		Relative standard deviation of the present method* (\pm , %)
	Present method	AAS method	
Kesari metal ^a	0.10	0.11	1.5
M P metal ^a	0.04	0.03	1.7
Singhania steel ^a	0.70	0.72	1.6
Swastik wires ^b	0.28	0.27	1.6
Coal ash ^c	521	523	1.5
Cement dust ^c	394	396	1.5

^aWater samples collected from Urla Industrial Estate, Raipur (M.P.).

^bWater samples were collected from Bhanpuri, Raipur (M.P.)

^cObtained from Mandhar Cement Factory, Raipur (M.P.)

*Average of six determinations.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena SPEKOL spectrophotometer equipped with 1-cm quartz cells and a Systronic 335 pH-meter were used.

A stock solution of manganese(II) was prepared by dissolving $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1.0 g) in double-distilled water (250 ml) containing 0.5 M HCl (2 ml) and working standard solution was prepared by dilution of the stock solution and standardised complexometrically⁵. A 0.01 M solution of *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPBA)⁶ in chloroform and a 0.004 M solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) in methanol were prepared. NaOH- H_3BO_3 buffer solution⁷ of pH 9.0 and 10.0 and 10 M HCl were prepared respectively for pH and acidity adjustment of the solution.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck/SD Fine Chem.).

Extraction of Mn^{II} with HDPBA: An aliquot of the test

solution (containing upto 24.0 μg of Mn^{II}) was taken. The pH of the 10 ml final aqueous solution was adjusted to 9.0 ± 0.2 by adding buffer solution. The solution was shaken with chloroform solution of HDPBA (5 ml; 0.3% w/v) for 2 min. The organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, made upto 10 ml with chloroform, and its absorbance measured against reagent blank at 400 nm.

Spectrophotometric determination of Mn^{II} with PAN:

The test solution (containing upto 10.5 μg of Mn^{II}) was extracted with HDPBA as above. The Mn^{II} from Mn^{II} -HDPBA complex in chloroform was stripped to the aqueous phase with 2 M HCl (2 ml). The organic phase was discarded and PAN solution (2 ml) was added to the aqueous phase. The pH of the aqueous solution was adjusted to 10.0 ± 0.2 using borate buffer solution, the volume made upto 15 ml with distilled water and its absorbance measured against reagent blank at 555 nm.

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